

JACK LONDON'S JOURNALISM OF ARTISTIC ELEMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11101309>

Jack London's novel "Martin Eden" talks about the inner world of man, hard work, and struggle for life. These qualities are embodied in the character of Martin in the novel [1]. The purpose of the article is to determine the uniqueness of the artistic world in Jack London's work. In 1900-1910, the writer translated his works in connection with the specific features of the interpretation of "man-nature-civilization" problems [2].

He is an American writer who has written fiction and non-fiction books, short stories, poems, plays, and essays. Jack London was born in San Francisco, California. His mother, Flora Wellman, was living with William Chaney, a lawyer and astrologer, and became pregnant with Jack. Jack London had socialist views. These ideas are reflected in his writing, speeches, and other activities. He was a member of the Socialist Workers Party and the Socialist Party of America. He was a socialist candidate who ran for mayor of Oakland in 1901 and 1905, but he did not receive the necessary votes to get elected. In 1906, he gave speeches on several socialist topics around the country. Among his best-known works are Call of the Wild and White Tooth, both Klondike Gold Rush, as well as the short stories To Build a Fire, A Northern Odyssey, and Love of Life. He also wrote about the South Pacific "Pearls of Parlay" and "Heathen". The term literary journalism is sometimes used interchangeably, not creatively; However, it is often seen as a form of creativity. Jack London wrote about romanticism and the difficulties of ordinary life in his works. London was one of the first writers to gain worldwide fame and fortune by writing a single work. Jack London published his first two novels, The Dazzler's Cruise and Snow Maiden, in 1902. A year later, at the age of 27, he achieved commercial success with his best-known novel, The Challenge. Savage is a short adventure novel set in the 1890s during the Klondike Gold Rush, set during London's year in the Yukon and centered around a Saint Bernard-Scotch shepherd named Buck. The book remains in print today. London was part of the radical literary group The Crowd in San Francisco and a passionate advocate of trade unionism, workers' rights, socialism, and eugenics. He has written several works on similar themes, such as the dystopian novel The Iron Heel, his fiction expose The Abyss, Class War, and Before Adam. Jack London's works are famous all over the world, his works reflect the colorfulness of life, the glorification of love, and the struggle of people with wild nature. Jack London's work is diverse - protest against the bourgeois system, socialist ideas, individualism, and even themes of peace and stability in the last years of his work can be seen in his works. London's first creative work and essay "Typhoon off the coast of Japan" was awarded and presented on November 12, 1893.

London often portrays uncivilized Indians and Pacific peoples as innocent, strong, and courageous people. London shows them as incomparable romantics and praises their natural enthusiasm, courage, and readiness to fight for life ("Northern Odyssey", "The Legend of Kische", "White Silence", etc.). London's "White Silence" - incomparably glorifies those who overcome the snow and can withstand the harsh weather. Martin Eden is a book about a victim of love who found his life path through the great power and human tenacity of his accidental love, which eventually led him to maturity, but which guaranteed his inevitable doom. Despite this, he is a simple ship captain who can show what a person can and can achieve in life. The high peak of maturity is due to his unattainable original love and the ability to love the beauty that lies dormant

in the corner of his heart. Jack London had socialist views. These views were evident in his writing, speeches, and other activities. He was a member of the Socialist Labor Party and the Socialist Party of America. He was the Socialist candidate for mayor of Auckland in 1901 and 1905, but he did not receive the necessary votes to be elected. In 1906, he gave several lectures on socialist topics around the country and also published several essays sharing his socialist views.

Although books are more common today than movies, this was not the case in Jack London's day. He was one of the first writers to work on film when his novel *The Wolf-Wolf* was made into the first full-length American film. London was also a pioneer in the science fiction genre. To do this, he wrote about apocalyptic catastrophes, future wars, and scientific dystopias before the usual. Later science fiction writers, such as George Orwell, cited London books, including *Adam* and *The Iron Heel*, as influences on their work. Jack London died on November 22, 1916, at the age of 40 at his home in California. About his death, some people claimed that he committed suicide. However, he suffered from many health problems later in life and the official cause of death was listed as kidney disease.

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